

IMPROVEMENT OF STRATEGIC PLANNING OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN "RF BROTHER" LLC.

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***Abstract.** In this article, the use of strategic planning and management methods in hotels, gaining knowledge and skills in the field of service and tourism, strengthening marketing research in the hotel, entering as much and more complete information as possible into the hotel website, its enrichment is considered.*

***Keywords:** tourism, hotel, service, skills, management, strategy, competition.*

INTRODUCTION. The hotel industry is a component of the tourism industry. Therefore, the development of tourism leads to the expansion of hotel activities. World practice shows that tourism contributes to general economic growth and the development of underdeveloped regions. Opening of tourist centers in such areas is the main method of economic development of many countries. The establishment of tourist centers in mountain and rural areas will contribute to the development of these areas and the improvement of the standard of living of the population.

Despite the fact that Uzbekistan has rich tourist resources, the level of use of the available opportunities is much less than required. Another important aspect of this sector is that it is also an important sector that helps to solve the problem of providing employment to surplus labor force in rural areas. Because many traditional services that are attractive for private entrepreneurship are not sufficiently developed in the city or in the countryside. Especially in rural areas, until recently, no effective measures were taken for the development of this sector.

Royal Hotel Samarkand is located on Babur Mirza Street in Samarkand and was opened in October 2020. The hotel meets the requirements of 4-star hotels. The hotel has 32 rooms. These include Deluxe, Deluxe and Standard rooms. Breakfast (buffet table) is included in the price for guests. The hotel is mainly visited by guests from Russia, Spain, Turkey and Portugal, as well as local tourists.

The hotel's restaurant, called "Royal Terrace", offers guests high-quality service and a menu of European dishes. It can host a party of 80 people at the same time and also organize a party for the photo session of the bride and groom.

The hotel has a total of 5 employees in the reception department, and Excel spreadsheets are used for the department's operation and room management, and the room keys are touch-sensitive, and their management is entrusted to the administrators. Guests who come to the hotel visit by phone, through the Booking.com website, through contracts with travel agencies. Large orders and their location are handled by the hotel Booking manager.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results One room is allocated for the Hotel Housekeeping department on each floor, where the necessary equipment and tools are located. The Housekeeping Manager is responsible for their account and the condition of the rooms.

Main customers

"Sogda tour" tourist company, Tourist company "Dolores", "Marakanda Travel" tourist company and prestigious organizations and enterprises in the city of Samarkand are located at #46 Bobur Mirzo Street.

Equipment of hotel rooms

- Air conditioning in every room
- Closet for clothes
- TV set
- Tea, coffee
- Dishes and plates
- Electric water heater
- Suitcase holder
- Desk and chair for work
- Shower or bath
- Various cleaning products

Hotel options

The Royal Hotel is currently one of the most prestigious hotels in Samarkand, and it surpasses other hotels by combining quality and services. Thanks to this, the new hotel now has enough customers, and top companies and state organizations are recommending our hotel to their guests.

Another advantage of the hotel is that it is located in a relatively quiet place, which allows a guest who is tired of walking during the day to have a quiet rest at night.

Currently, there are different opinions about what the main goal of management should be, and what criteria should be used to calculate its effectiveness. It is generally accepted that the final product of the activity of the administrative apparatus is one or another decision. At the same time, the main goal of the management system is to get additional income, products, etc. All this ultimately leads to attempts to determine the effectiveness of the management system directly through the results obtained in the main business area. In addition, an effective system of management is interrelated economic,

The task of improving marketing-management efficiency is of crucial importance for enterprises of various ownership forms and for enterprises managed by external companies, which are common in the hotel business. In this regard, it is important to improve the structure of the administrative apparatus and reduce duplication in the work of departments.

Solving the problems of improving marketing management creates the need to develop effective criteria for evaluating management efficiency. Therefore, the problem of choosing such a criterion is one of the most urgent issues both in the theory of management and in the implementation of the management process in specific organizations. In the case of a hotel company, the need to determine performance evaluation criteria can be implemented in various areas of management: when developing an organization development strategy, justifying specific measures for improving management, evaluating the management performance of individual employees, management departments in the hospitality industry.

The operation of hotel enterprises in modern conditions requires accurate planning of their activities, as well as an understanding of the nature of the tasks that must be solved by the management staff to ensure the successful operation of these enterprises. In this regard, first of all,

strategic analysis of various aspects of their activity, including the development of new competitive strategies taking into account the specific features of their application depending on the specific characteristics of hotel enterprises, improving the organizational structure of the enterprise we believe that it is appropriate to clearly define the guidelines in the field of program preparation and development planning. enterprises, in particular, investment policy.

On the other hand, conducting a strategic analysis is a strategic management tool, which involves adding the potential of the enterprise by planning its strategy based on the forecast of the future environment. Such a concept of management requires management staff to be ready for fundamental changes, risks and focus on creative development of new opportunities. Achieving the goals of the enterprise therefore depends on the effectiveness of three main factors: the chosen strategy, organizational structure and comprehensive planning of the enterprise.

As part of a systems approach, planning is viewed as a continuously evolving process. This suggests that the future state of the hotel industry and its components is uncertain and cannot be predicted from current or past conditions (resource approach).

In this case, the emphasis is on creating alternative future scenarios based on today's actions, and not simply on adapting to what the future may bring. In addition, planning should be based on a number of methodological principles: systematic, comprehensive, optimality, flexibility, constraints Strategic management

The logical development of planning activities leads to strategic planning.

The strategic form of planning is characterized by a number of features:

First, strategic planning is based on a systemic approach and considers the hotel industry as a complex and dynamic system.

Secondly, such planning is a logical development of the ideas of long-term planning and is clearly focused on the long-term perspective.

Thirdly, this form of planning ensures the identification of the main directions of development of any element of the hotel industry, and then reflects certain gaps for economic activity, which must be filled with operational planning tools. Fourth, the main objective of strategic planning should be to promote the future development potential of any element of the hotel industry.

The planning function, as is known, is the stage of the management process, within which the objectives of the activities necessary for these tools are determined, as well as the most effective methods in the specific working conditions of hotel enterprises. Therefore, it is recommended to dwell on the problems in the activity planning system during the study of the strategic analysis process. It should be noted that in relation to enterprises in the field of hospitality, this issue remains more relevant due to the lack of attention paid to the development of development plans for these enterprises in the past. This fact has significantly reduced and continues to reduce the efficiency of such enterprises.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The high level of service of this hotel simultaneously serves the development of the tourism sector. The reason is that depending on the same hotel, other hotels will start providing high service.

On the example of the "Royal Hotel" hotel, a number of conclusions and scientific recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the use of strategic management in the management of service processes have been developed, which are expressed in the following:

1. The peculiarities of the management structures and management methods of the hotels operating in our country were studied. Along with the appropriate living conditions in the hotels, the quality of the management of the service departments should be at a high level.

2. Another characteristic aspect for local guests is that the price of accommodation in hotels intended for their stay should be set much cheaper. Observations show that most local guests try to stay with their relatives or prefer to stay in a rental. When they were surveyed, it was found that most of them note that the prices of hotels are expensive. This situation requires that in the development of the hotel industry in the city, they should make appropriate changes and take into account the local demand. Based on these conclusions, we can make the following suggestions.

➤ Using the same strategic planning and management methods in hotels as in manufacturing enterprises.

➤ Conducting retraining of hotel employees to acquire knowledge and skills in the field of service and tourism.

➤ Recruiting qualified specialists in the field of management to improve hotel management.

➤ Establishing cooperative relations and sharing experience with other enterprises in order to improve the qualifications of employees.

➤ Strengthening hotel marketing research.

➤ It is necessary to enrich the hotel site by entering as much and more complete information as possible.

➤ Using modern advertising methods, it is necessary to attract not only foreign tourists, but also citizens of Uzbekistan to come to the hotel.

➤ It is necessary to improve the quality of services provided in the hotel and introduce new types of services.

➤ It is to inculcate a spirit of dedication and a responsible approach to the performance of the employees.

➤ It is possible to reduce the cost of services in the hotel and attract customers in this way.

➤ It is necessary to introduce working in uniform and specific work clothes for hotel employees.

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